

Synthesis and Investigate Yb-Doping Effect on Crystal Structure of Multiferroic Material BaYFeO₄

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ABSTRACT

Multiferroics with strong magnetoelectric coupling, which allow their application in multifunctional devices due to electric-field-tunable magnetism and magnetic-field-controlled ferroelectricity, are of great interest. Notable among these are BaRFeO₄ materials (where Rare rare-earth elements), with BaYFeO₄ being thoroughly studied and yielding important results. In this work, we investigate the effect of Yb-doping on the physical properties of BaYFeO₄ material. The BaY_{1-x}Yb_xFeO₄ (x = 0, 0.125, 0.250, 0.375, 0.500, 1) system was fabricated by the solid-state reaction method. This is an isostructural system with an orthorhombic structure belonging to the Pnma symmetry group. The effect of Yb-doping on the crystal structure and surface morphology of BaY_{1-x}Yb_xFeO₄ has been investigated in detail.

I. INTRODUCTION

The rapid development of science and technology nowadays requires advanced research and manufacturing technologies for materials to not only meet high-quality standards but also to be highly versatile and multifunctional. Multifunctional materials help optimize the size and compactness of components and devices while still meeting all criteria for sensitivity and flexibility. Among the diverse range of integrated materials, multiferroic materials with strong magnetoelectric coupling between magnetic and ferroelectric properties are the most favored due to their high applicability. Recent discoveries of this correlation in many materials such as ACr₂O₄ (A = Ni, Fe) [1, 2] [3], AV₂O₄ (A = Zn, Cd, Mn), and Mn₃O₄ [4], provide valuable insights into the understanding of the magnetoelectric effect in multiferroic materials.

ABFeO₄ systems also attract special attention due to the diverse findings regarding the mechanism and origin of ferroelectricity. Specifically, BaYFeO₄ material exhibits strong magnetic frustration due to the peculiar crystal structure, displaying complex magnetic properties with three magnetic phase transitions of Fe³⁺ magnetic moments [5, 6]. Typically, for these materials, the magnetic and related ferroelectric phases show similar transformation trends. However, the ferroelectric phase and long-range magnetic order states in BaYFeO₄ material exhibit completely different trends under an external magnetic field. In a recent

publication [7], we demonstrated that the transformation trend of the ferroelectric phase under a magnetic field is related to the change in spin correlation from antiferromagnetic spin-glass to ferromagnetic. However, Belik and colleagues published results on the ferroelectric and magnetic properties of the isostructural BaDyFeO₄ material [8], which are completely different from BaYFeO₄. The existence of the ferroelectric phase was not detected in this material, suggesting it may be related to the magnetic phase transformation in BaDyFeO₄. The differences in physical properties between these isostructural materials highlight the important role of the rare-earth element R. Therefore, it is necessary to further investigate the role of R in the mechanism of the physical properties of the entire system.

In this work, we doped Yb into Y positions of BaYFeO₄ material and study Yb-doping effect to its crystal structure and morphology. Specifically, the obtained material system is BaY_{1-x}Yb_xFeO₄ (x = 0, 0.125; 0.250; 0.375, 0.500, 1) with the results presented in detail below.

II. EXPERIMENT

The research system is BaY_{1-x}Yb_xFeO₄ (x = 0, 0.125; 0.250; 0.375, 0.500, 1) materials, which were synthesized by the solid-reaction method. The precursors BaCO₃ (99,997%), Fe₂O₃ (99,9%), Y₂O₃ (99,99%), Yb₂O₃ (99,99%) were weighed according to the equation:

where $x=0, 0.125, 0.250, 0.375, 0.500, 1$. The precursor mixture was pre-calcined at 900°C for 12 hours and sintered at 1250°C for 24 hours. The sintering step was repeated several times to increase crystallinity, with thorough grinding and mixing between each sintering. X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements were performed on a D8 Advance Eco (Bruker) system with a Cu-K α radiation source ($\lambda = 1.54056 \text{ \AA}$) in the 2θ range of 10 - 70°. XRD data were refined using the Rietveld method with Fullprof software. The surface morphology was examined through scanning electron microscopy (SEM) imaging on a JSM-IT2000 (JOEL, Horiba) scanning electron microscope.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The XRD patterns of the BaY_{1-x}Yb_xFeO₄ system is shown in Figure 1. The results indicate that they are similar to XRD pattern of BaYFeO₄ material, with an orthorhombic crystal structure belonging to the *Pnma* symmetry group. There is a minor impurity, corresponding to the peak at the position $2\theta = 30.84^\circ$ which, according to previous research, is the peak of BaFeO₃.

Figure 1. XRD patterns of BaY_{1-x}Yb_xFeO₄ system ($x=0.125; 0.250; 0.375, 0.500, 1$).

The orthorhombic crystal structure of BaYFeO₄ consists of alternating corner-sharing octahedra Fe³⁺O₆ and square pyramids Fe³⁺O₅, forming into Fe₄O₁₈ rings which form columns propagating along the *b* axis.

The orthorhombic structure of this material system is composed of square pyramidal Fe³⁺O₅ and alternating corner-sharing octahedral Fe³⁺O₆, with Fe³⁺ ions at the center and O²⁻ ions at the vertices. The FeO₅ pyramids and FeO₆ octahedra are connected to form Fe₄O₁₈ rings. These Fe₄O₁₈ rings are linked and stacked along the *b*-axis, forming hollow columns, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The hollow column structure of BaYFeO₄ is formed from Fe₄O₁₈ rings.

The XRD data were refined using Fullprof software according to the Rietveld theory [9]. The lattice parameters and atomic positions are detailed in Table 1 for the concentration $x = 0.125$. The results indicate that Yb doping does not alter the crystal structure of the original BaYFeO₄ material, and Yb ions effectively substitute for Y ions, as evidenced by the good fit of the *Pnma* structural model.

Table 1. Atomic positions in crystal structure of BaY_{0.875}Yb_{0.125}FeO₄

Atom	Site	x	y	z
Ba1	4c	0.211(8)	0.25	0.674(4)
Ba2	4c	0.414(1)	0.25	0.395(4)
Y1	4c	0.415(2)	0.25	0.014(2)
Yb1	4c	0.415(2)	0.25	0.014(2)
Y2	4c	0.142(5)	0.25	0.309(4)
Yb2	4c	0.142(5)	0.25	0.309(4)
Fe1	4c	0.470(1)	0.25	0.718(1)
Fe2	4c	0.191(2)	0.25	0.022(5)
O1	4c	0.579(1)	0.25	0.613(6)
O2	4c	0.294(8)	0.25	0.183(7)
O3	8d	0.004(6)	0.496(5)	0.359(6)
O4	8d	0.215(8)	0.517(1)	0.444(3)
O5	8d	0.111(3)	0.006(4)	0.133(4)

$a=13.1194 \text{ \AA}, b=5.6833 \text{ \AA}, c=10.2279 \text{ \AA}$

The lattice parameters and unit cell volume of the BaY_{1-x}Yb_xFeO₄ system are shown in Figure 3. It can be observed that the dimensions decrease with increasing Yb concentration, and the unit cell volume also decreases accordingly.

Figure 3. Lattical parameters and unit cell volume of BaY_{1-x}Yb_xFeO₄ change according to Yb-doping concentration.

Additionally, from the XRD patterns, the average crystallite size and microstrain in the BaY_{1-x}Yb_xFeO₄ material system were determined using the Williamson-Hall (W-H) method [10]. According to the Williamson-Hall method, there are three factors that cause the broadening of diffraction peaks:

(i) peak broadening due to the small crystallite size, with the full width at half maximum (FWHM) determined by the formula:

$$\beta_D = \frac{K\lambda}{D \cos\theta} \quad (1)$$

where K is the shape factor (typically valued at 0.9), λ is the X-ray wavelength, and D is the average crystallite size;

(ii) peak broadening due to microstrain in the material:

$$\beta_\epsilon = 4\epsilon \tan\theta \quad (2)$$

where ε is the root mean square value of the microstrain;

(iii) broadening due to the measurement equipment. Let β_{hkl} be the FWHM of the diffraction peak for the plane with Miller indices hkl after subtracting the instrumental broadening. We have:

$$\beta_{hkl} = \beta_D + \beta_\epsilon = \frac{K\lambda}{D \cos\theta_{hkl}} + 4\epsilon \tan\theta_{hkl} \quad (3)$$

Multiplying both sides of the above equation by cosθ_{hkl}, we obtain:

$$\beta_{hkl} \cos\theta_{hkl} = \frac{K\lambda}{D} + 4\epsilon \sin\theta_{hkl} \quad (4)$$

From this equation, we see that the plot describing the dependence of β_{hkl} cosθ_{hkl} on 4sinθ_{hkl} is a straight line with a slope of ε and an intercept at Kλ/D. Therefore, using the Williamson-Hall method, we can determine the average crystallite size and microstrain in the material. The results applied to the BaY_{1-x}Yb_xFeO₄ system are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. The dependence of β_{hkl}.cos(θ_{hkl}) on 4sin(θ_{hkl}) of BaY_{1-x}Yb_xFeO₄ system.

The crystallite size and microstrain of the BaY_{1-x}Yb_xFeO₄ system are presented in Figure 5. The results show that the crystallite size of the materials tends to decrease, while their microstrain increases with augmentation of Yb-doping concentration x. The microstrain in the material is attributed to the difference in ionic radii between Y and Yb (Y³⁺ ≈ 0.9 Å, Yb³⁺ ≈ 1.1 Å). When Yb is doped into the BaYFeO₄, Yb³⁺ ions replace Y³⁺ ions. Due to the larger ionic radius of Yb³⁺ compared to Y³⁺, the surrounding space at the Yb³⁺ position is distorted. As the Yb doping concentration increases, this distortion also increases, as shown in Figure 5b.

Figure 5. Average crystallite size and microstrain of BaY_{1-x}Yb_xFeO₄ system.

The surface morphology of BaY_{1-x}Yb_xFeO₄ materials was studied through SEM images, as shown in Figure 6. The BaY_{1-x}Yb_xFeO₄ materials exhibit similar morphologies, consisting of rod-shaped grains interspersed with grains that tend to be spherical. SEM images reveal the heterogeneous nature of morphology and grain size within each sample of the material system. The average grain size ranges from 4.078 μm to 5.915 μm, with a predicted variation trend according to the function y = -9.2374x³+9.0134x²+1.0096x+4.1631 where x is the Yb doping concentration and y is the grain size, as shown in Figure 7.

Figure 6. SEM micrograph of BaY_{1-x}Yb_xFeO₄ system.

Figure 7. The dependence of particle size of BaY_{1-x}Yb_xFeO₄ system on Yb concentration.

IV. CONCLUSION

The BaY_{1-x}Yb_xFeO₄ material system was fabricated using the solid-state reaction method. The effect of Yb doping on the crystal properties of the BaY_{1-x}Yb_xFeO₄ system has been studied in detail. As the Yb doping concentration increases, both the lattice parameters and unit cell volume decrease. Meanwhile, the average crystallite size tends to decrease, and the microstrain increases. This is believed to be related to the distortions around the Y site when Yb replaces it. The entire system exhibits relatively similar surface morphologies, and the grain size changes as a function of the doping concentration. All these changes will directly affect the bond lengths between ions in the material, leading to changes in the internal magnetic interactions. Further, more specific studies are needed to understand the impact of this doping on other physical properties of the system.

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